

Eu₂SrCo_{1.5}Fe_{0.5}O₇ a new promising Ruddlesden–Popper member as cathode component for intermediate temperature solid oxide fuel cells

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Abstract

A new oxide of the Ruddlesden–Popper series in the $(\text{Eu,Sr})_{n+1}(\text{Co,Fe})_n\text{O}_{3n+1}$ system has been isolated and structurally characterized. X-ray diffraction and electron microscopy show that polycrystalline $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ constitutes the $n=2$ member of a homologous series, the essential feature of which is the existence of two connected Co/Fe octahedral layers with perovskite-like structure, linked by an EuO rock-salt like layer. Random distribution of 3d-metals in the perovskite blocks and interstitial and oxygen vacancies in the rock-salt layers (anti Frenkel defects) are observed by Electron Microscopy. Such facts are commonly associated to high electronic conduction and ionic conductivity. The electrochemical study shows that the area-specific resistance of this compound is $0.26 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ at $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in air, a value which is comparable to that of the best state-of-the-art Ruddlesden–Popper materials used as cathode in intermediate temperature solid oxide fuel cells.

Introduction

Materials to be used as cathode component in solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) have to promote the reduction of molecular oxygen to oxygen anions (Oxygen Reduction Reaction, ORR) on the cathode-surface. These ions must diffuse through the cathode to the electrolyte, so sufficient ionic conductivity is convenient.¹ In ORR, electrons also participate in the reaction, and a cathode with high electronic conductivity is therefore required to minimize ohmic losses. Normally, electrical conductivity greater than 100 S cm^{-1} is required.² Thus, mixed ionic-electronic conductors (MIEC) are preferred. The electrode materials should be mechanical and chemical compatible with other components of the fuel cell, such as electrolyte and interconnectors. For the former, all the components should have similar thermal expansion coefficient (TEC) ca. $(12\text{-}14 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1})$ are the typical values for most common electrolytes such as $\text{Gd}_{0.10}\text{Ce}_{0.90}\text{O}_{2-\delta}$ (CGO) and $\text{La}_{0.9}\text{Sr}_{0.1}\text{Ga}_{0.8}\text{Mg}_{0.2}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (LSGM).³ Chemical compatibility with other cell components ensures minimal ohmic losses due to the formation of non-conductive compounds and long-term stability. Finally, but of paramount importance, the electrode should possess high catalytic activity for oxygen reduction. For practical application the electrode should have an area-specific electrode polarization resistance (ASR) lower than $0.15 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ ⁴ at working temperature. This value can be achieved by several materials at sufficient high temperature.⁵⁻⁹

Lowering the SOFC operating temperature down to intermediate values ($500^{\circ}\text{-}700^{\circ}\text{C}$) is an important challenge to develop real devices using low-cost materials for interconnectors and to improve cell-endurance. However, cathode-resistance may be a serious drawback for operation at intermediate temperatures since the above-discussed cathode properties strongly depend on temperature limiting the performance of the IT-SOFCs. Therefore, cathode materials showing high-performance at moderate temperatures are required for the development of IT-SOFCs.

It is well known from the 1970th that many oxides of general formula A_2MO_4 (A = rare-earth and/or alkaline-earth, M = 3d-metal) with K_2NiF_4 -like structure show high electronic conductivity as well as interstitial mobile oxide ions.¹⁰⁻¹³ The K_2NiF_4 structure belongs to the Ruddlesden-Popper (R-P) series^{14, 15} with the general formula $\text{A}_{n+1}\text{M}_n\text{O}_{3n+1}((\text{AMO}_3)_n\text{AO})$ (A = rare-earth and/or alkaline-earth elements and M = transition metal), in which the multiple perovskite layers that are n-octahedra thick alternate with single AO rock salt layers (see Figure 1). Electronic conduction may occur in perovskite-like blocks, built up from corner-sharing MO_6 octahedra, when M-cations occupying the center of the polyhedra can present multiple non-localised oxidation states. Besides, AO rock-salt layers may present anionic vacancies and/or interstitial oxygen ions, both defects resulting in ionic conduction. As stated above, those are desirable features for SOFC cathode materials. However, only recently, this kind of materials have been studied as candidates for this application.¹⁶⁻¹⁹ and some of them show good preformaces as cathode materials for IT-SOFCs.²⁰⁻²³ Among the R-P series, the interest has been mainly focused on the n=1 intergrowth oxides, where one-octahedron-thick layer alternate with single AO rock salt layer along packing axis, though there are some articles reporting the properties of n=2 and 3 members.²⁴⁻³⁰

In general, Co-R-P oxides exhibit high catalytic activity for oxygen reduction and high electronic conductivity but relatively high thermal expansion coefficients (TEC), like the Co-perovskites, mainly due to spin transitions.^{31, 32} Substitution of Co by Cu or Fe

decreases TEC, however, decreases the electronic conductivity albeit increases the area specific resistance.^{16, 33-35}

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the crystal structure of Ruddlesden–Popper series corresponding to $n=1$, 2 and 3, consisting of a block of n perovskite-like layers separated by a layer of NaCl structure.

As a continuation of our previous works,^{26, 27} in this paper, the oxide of composition $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$, a new member $n=2$ of Ruddlesden–Popper series $(\text{Eu},\text{Sr})_{n+1}(\text{Co},\text{Fe})_n\text{O}_{3n+1}$, has been prepared and a detailed structural characterisation by X-ray diffraction and electron microscopy is presented. Besides, its electrical and electrochemical properties as cathode for IT-SOFCs have been explored. The present material provides new and relevant information on the effect of substitution of cobalt by other 3d-metal (iron in this case) on material features such as TEC, catalytic activity for ORR (through ASR) and MIEC properties at high temperature, which are of paramount importance for the performance of a given material as cathode component of SOFC.

Experimental

Polycrystalline $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ (ESCF1550) was synthesized by heating stoichiometric amounts of SrCO_3 (Aldrich 99.98%), Co_3O_4 (Aldrich 99.9%) and Eu_2O_3 (Aldrich 99+%) / Fe_2O_3 (Aldrich 99+%) in air at 1250°C for 5 days, and then quenched to room temperature. Sample purity was determined by powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) (these data were also used for the structure characterization) on a Bruker D8 high-resolution diffractometer equipped with a LynxEye® fast detector using monochromatic $\text{CuK}\alpha_1$ ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) radiation obtained with a germanium primary monochromator. The angular range, step size and counting times were selected so as to ensure the required data quality and resolution for

structural refinement. Diffraction data were analysed using the Fullprof software; ³⁶ peak shape was described by a pseudo-Voigt function, and the background level was fitted with linear interpolation.

The sample was characterized by High Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy (HRTEM) by using a JEOLJEM-3000F electron microscope operated at 300kV. Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (STEM) was performed on a JEOL JEM-ARM200cF microscope (Cold Field Emission Gun) operated at 200 kV. The microscope is provided with a spherical aberration corrector in the electron probe (probe current ~ 20pA for a probe size ~0.8 Å, convergence semi-angle ~25 mrad, collection semi-angles of 90-170 mrad for High Angle Annular Dark Field (HAADF) STEM imaging and 11-22 mrad for Annular Bright Field (ABF) STEM imaging). Local composition was analysed by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) with an INCA Oxford analyser system attached to above mentioned electron microscopes.

The average oxidation state of 3d-ions (Co and Fe) and oxygen content (assuming charge neutrality) of samples were determined by titration as described in the literature³⁷ and Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) on a Netzsch 409PC apparatus by heating at 10C min⁻¹ from RT to 1000 °C in air. This latter also provides information on oxygen stoichiometry stability from RT to working conditions (up to 900 °C).

Total electrical conductivity of dense bars was determined by d.c. four-probe method in air, O₂ and N₂ atmospheres on rectangular bars. Using a potentiostat/galvanostat equipment working in galvanostatic mode (Autolab PGSTAT302N) a current in the range 50-500 mA was applied through the external surfaces of the bar covered with a Pt layer and connected to Pt wires to produce homogeneous current flux through the sample. Another pair of Pt wires was attached to the sample at a one to each other to record the voltage drop associated to the volumetric resistance between them. Samples were maintained at 950 °C for 12 h in the different atmosphere and measurements were recorded from this temperature to 200 °C (cooling rate of 5 °C min⁻¹) every 50 °C after stabilization for 15 min. Experimental resistances were obtained by the slope of V-I linear plot.

Chemical compatibility of ESCF1550 with the CGO was proven prior to the electrochemical studies: ESCF1550:CGO mixture (70:30 wt %) was heated at 900 °C for 12 hours and further analysed by PXRD. The microstructure of the electrochemical cells was evaluated by scanning electron microscopy before and after the impedance measurements using a FEI XL30 scanning electron microscope.

The electrochemical performance of SrEu₂Co_{1.5}Fe_{0.5}O₇ as cathode in IT-SOFCs has been evaluated by determination of the ASR of symmetrical two-electrode configuration cells at different temperatures in air by impedance spectroscopy (IS). Electrolyte pellets of about 8.6 mm diameter and around 1.10 mm thickness of commercial CGO (Fuel Cells Materials) were prepared by pressing the powder at 250 MPa and sintering in air at 1400 °C for 12 hours (heating/cooling rate of 2.5 °Cmin⁻¹). Thin layers of slurries of composite ESCF1550:CGO (70:30 wt%) using DecofluxTM as a binder were deposited onto both surfaces of the electrolyte pellet and then fired at 900 °C for 3h in air (heating/cooling rate of 2.5 °Cmin⁻¹). Silver paste and silver mesh were used as current collectors. The IS spectra were obtained in air on heating and cooling cycles between 550 °C and 700 °C using a frequency response analyser (Solartron 1255 + dielectric interface 1296) in the frequency range 0.1 Hz to 1 MHz with an excitation voltage of 50 mV. The impedance spectra were

fitted to equivalent circuits using the Zview software³⁸. The ASR values (resistance associated to the total electrochemical processes at the electrodes) have been determined from the resistance obtained by extracting the electrolyte and measuring-device resistances, corrected for the electrode area and divided by 2, as it is common in symmetrical cells.^{1, 39}

Results and Discussion

Structural Characterisation

The sample of nominal composition $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ was confirmed to be single phase by PXRD since the whole pattern can be indexed with a tetragonal unit cell with lattice parameters $a=5.3925(1)$ Å and $c=19.5552(6)$ Å. The reflection conditions ($(0kl)$ $k+l=2n$, $(0k0)$ $k=2n$ and $(00l)$ $l=2n$) allow determining as possible Space Groups (S.G.): $P4_2nm$ (#102), $P-4n2$ (#118) or $P4_2/mnm$ (#136). This latter S.G. is used to describe the structure of $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrFe}_2\text{O}_7$ oxide.⁴⁰⁻⁴²

Selected Area Electron Diffraction (SAED) patterns and HRTEM micrographs along several zone axes were taken on crystals of $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ in order to fully reconstruct the reciprocal and real space lattices. The most relevant zone axis, corresponding to $[-110]$ and $[010]$ are shown in Figure 2. All reflections (inset in Figures 2a and 2b) can be indexed in the primitive tetragonal lattice determined by PXRD ($a=5.4$ Å and $c=19.5$ Å); moreover, the observed reflection conditions confirm the possible symmetries deduced from PXRD. The HRTEM micrograph taken along $[-110]$ (Figure 2a) shows an apparently well-ordered material with d-spacing of 3.8 Å and 19.5 Å, corresponding to d_{110} and d_{001} . The contrast observed in this image corresponds to bright dots alternating with a brightest one, which can be associated to the Sr/Eu atoms alternating with Co/Fe ones along $[001]$, as shown in the model outlined in the figure. Such contrast variation is characteristic of $n=2$ member of Ruddlesden–Popper series, as indicated in references.^{41, 42} No evidence of microdomains, neither extra spots nor diffuse scattering that could be a sign of additional order were observed in the corresponding diffraction patterns or Fourier transforms of the HRTEM images.

Figure 2. (a) HRTEM image of $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ along the $[-110]$ zone axis. Inset show corresponding optical Fourier transform (FT). (b) HRTEM image of along the $[010]$ zone axis. Insets show the corresponding optical Fourier transform (FT) along each zone axis and Magnification of the image where metal atoms are superimposed.

The HRTEM micrograph taken along the [010] direction (Figure 2b), also reveals a well-ordered material with d-spacings of 2.7 Å and 9.8 Å, corresponding to d_{200} and d_{002} . Fourier transform was performed on the micrograph with the aim of looking for the presence of different domains that could evidence the existence of additional ordering or intergrowth of different members of Ruddlesden–Popper series. Since no extra spots, or diffuse scattering are observed, any kind of additional order can be discarded. The contrast variation confirms that this compound presents the structure of the $n=2$ member of Ruddlesden–Popper series.

To elucidate in detail the structure of $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ compound, a HAADF and ABF STEM study with atomic resolution has been performed. HAADF-STEM imaging provides images of the crystal structure which in most cases are directly interpretable: the contrast is roughly proportional to the average Z^n ($n \sim 1.7$) of the atomic columns being imaged,⁴³⁻⁴⁶ however, the oxygen (and other light elements) columns are barely visible in the presence of heavier atoms. A HAADF-STEM image along [010] is shown in Figure 3a, the atomically resolved columns corresponding to Eu, Sr and Co/Fe, are clearly observed arranged in an ordered intergrowth along the c-axis. The brightest dots are related to the heaviest Eu atoms, whereas those of intermediate intensity are Sr and the less intense ones correspond to Fe/Co atoms. These structural features agree with those reported for $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrFe}_2\text{O}_7$ ⁴⁰.

Figure 3b shows the ABF STEM image that was recorded simultaneously. This imaging mode allows reliably revealing both light and heavy atom columns over a range of thickness and defocus values.^{43, 46} In contrast to HAADF imaging, both light and heavy atom columns are imaged as dark spots.^{44, 45} However, this imaging technique does not provide a direct correspondence between contrast and $\sim Z^2$ as HAADF. In any case, the structural models obtained by both techniques nicely match. Even more, oxygen atoms are revealed as weak but clearly resolved spots. A schematic projection of the structure model of $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ compound based on that of $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrFe}_2\text{O}_7$ depicted in the inset of Figure 3b helps to interpret the contrasts observed. The oxygen positions are sufficiently clear in the experimental image to allow revealing subtle structural details such as tilting of the corner-sharing octahedral MO_6 ($M = \text{Co}, \text{Fe}$).

A schematic representation of the structure is superimposed on Fig 3b. Interestingly, interstitial oxygen atoms are clearly detected within rock-salt like EuO layers, which are indicated by blue arrows in the figure (3b).

Figure 3. (a) HAADF-STEM image of along $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ [0 1 0]. A schematic model for cationic position has been inserted. (b) Corresponding ABF-STEM image where cationic atoms are in black and green, oxygen are in red. Blue arrows indicate interstitial oxygen in the rock-salt layer.

Using the above results we have developed a structural model for $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ based on the structure of $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrFe}_2\text{O}_7$ ($n=2$ member of the R-P series of layered compounds) with symmetry $P4_2/mnm$ ⁴⁰. PXRD data have been used to confirm the validity of this model, derived from local techniques, to describe the average structure of the title compound. At this point it must be commented that neutron powder diffraction data were collected on D2B at ILL to deal with those structural features related to the oxygen substructure. Unfortunately, due to neutron absorption of Co and Eu no conclusive results were obtained from these data.

It is well established that partial ordering of Sr^{2+} and Ln^{3+} ions can occur in similar R-P oxides $\text{Sr}_{2-x}\text{Ln}_x\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_7$ along the two A-cations sites; the smaller lanthanides are mainly located in the rock-salt layers whereas larger Sr^{2+} prefer the A-sites in the perovskite blocks.⁴⁷ Thus, the Eu/Sr distribution over the two crystallographically distinct A-sites was refined and complete cationic ordering was determined. Since no evidence of Co/Fe order in the B sublattice was detected, both cations were randomly distributed over the octahedral

sites. The refinement was stable provided a Debye-Waller for each kind of atom was used (same for all the oxygens). Thus, it was possible to refine the positions and occupancies of all atoms (since Fe and Co are indistinguishable by XRD their contents were assumed as the nominal ones); given full population of all sites within the experimental error (including oxygen atoms). Thus, no vacancies are detected in the anion substructure; no interstitial oxygen atoms in the rock-salt layer have been observed. Interestingly, chemical titration suggests that the oxygen content is close to the nominal one with no extra oxygen, since the average oxidation state of 3d-metals is determined to be 2.99(2); assuming electroneutrality the oxygen content is 6.99(3). Random distribution of 3d-metals in high oxidation states is commonly associated to high electronic conduction in oxides, whereas mobile interstitial oxygen or vacancies enhance ionic conductivity, as observed in some R-P $n=1$ oxides (K_2NiF_4 -like structures).⁴⁸⁻⁵²

Figure 4 shows the graphic results of the fitting of the experimental X-ray diffraction pattern and the difference between observed and calculated data.

Figure 4. Experimental (red points), calculated (solid black line) and their difference (blue line at bottom) X-ray diffraction patterns for $Eu_2SrCo_{1.5}Fe_{0.5}O_7$. The vertical bars indicate the positions of the Bragg peaks.

The final refined structural parameters are collected in Table SI 1, whereas Table SI 2 shows some selected interatomic distances. The structure refinement confirms that it is isostructural with $Eu_2SrFe_2O_7$ ⁴⁰ in agreement with the HRTEM results. In Figure 5 a schematic representation of the structure is depicted.

Interestingly, in the cubic-perovskite-like blocks (i.e. corner-sharing octahedra), tilting of the BO_6 polyhedra occurs with a Glazer⁵³ scheme ($a^-a^0c^0$) (block at the bottom of the unit cell) and ($a^0a^0c^0$) /block at the middle of the cell. That is, in every two-layer blocks out-of-phase tilt occurs along one of the pseudo-perovskite axis, being the direction of tilting rotated by 90° from one block to the adjacent ones. Along the four-fold axis no tilt is produced. Similarly in other layered perovskites such as the 12R-type hexagonal

$\text{Sr}_3\text{NdNb}_3\text{O}_{12}$ the octahedra of the three-layer blocks are tilted along the Cartesian x , y and z axes of the pseudo cubic sub cell according to the $(a^-a^-a^-)$ tilt system.⁵⁴

Figure 5. (a) Schematic representation along the [110] direction of the structure of $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$, (b) view along [1-10] of the perovskite blocks and (c) view along the c -axis of those blocks. Co and Fe are located at the centre of red octahedra of oxygen atoms (small red balls); orange balls represent Sr ions whereas magenta ones correspond to Eu.

Unfortunately, other structural features strongly related with electrical properties (in particular with ionic conduction) such as the existence of anion vacancies and interstitial oxygen ions, cannot be fully established using XRD. On the contrary, Figure 3b suggests the presence of interstitial oxygen atoms located in between two Eu-O planes. Since the compound is stoichiometric with no extra oxygen, as determined by redox titration, these interstitial oxygens should be created by **anion Frenkel (anti Frenkel)** defects, in Kröger-Vink notation:

Worth to note, motion of both vacancies and interstitial oxygens has been proposed to explain oxygen diffusion in other R-P materials.^{52, 55}

Thermal stability and expansion. Compatibility with the electrolyte.

Prior to be used as components in IT-SOFC electrodes, the chemical stability (oxygen loss or uptake) of the title material as well as its compatibility with the electrolyte (CGO) was

evaluated in simulated processing and working conditions. Besides, the thermal expansion coefficient (TEC) was evaluated by XRD thermodiffraction from RT to 900°C.

Since $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ is prepared by quenching from high temperature (1250°C), it exists as a metastable phase at lower temperatures. Therefore, it is relevant to determine whether it evolves (decomposes) in the IT-SOFC conditions. A small amount of the material was fired at 800 °C for several days (14 days) and slowly cooled down to room temperature. The corresponding PXRD pattern (not shown) allowed discarding any decomposition. On the contrary, TGA analyses (Figure SI 1) in oxidizing atmosphere (air) reveals that the material experiences a small but significant oxygen loss at working temperatures. Thus, by heating to 1000°C the stoichiometry evolves from $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ (as determined by chemical titration) to an oxygen content of 6.79(2), i.e. about 5% of the oxygen positions are vacant. In this connection, in spite of this small oxygen loss the linear thermal expansion coefficient is similar to that of other R-P n=2 materials ($\alpha_a = 8.4(6) \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$, $\alpha_c = 39.5(6) \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$), being anisotropic with high expansion along the c-axis which is the direction of the stacking of perovskite-like layers.²⁶

$\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ oxide presents an excellent compatibility with CGO; in the PXRD pattern of a composite (70:30 wt %) heated at 900 °C for 12 hours (Figure 6) only the Bragg maxima due to these components are observed, discarding any reaction or decomposition and suggesting good long-term stability of these cathodes.

Figure 6. XRD pattern of a (70:30 wt%) mixture of $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ and CGO treated at 900 °C for 12 hours. The vertical bars indicate the positions of the Bragg peaks corresponding to $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ (upper row) and CGO (lower row).

Electrical conductivity

Figure 7 displays the electrical conductivity of the $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ as a function of temperature in different atmospheres. Total conductivity (electronic plus ionic) increases on heating, reaching a maximum at 750 °C in air and pure oxygen atmospheres. In the entire temperature range, conductivity increases with the oxidising character of the gas, which indicates p-type electronic conduction, i.e. holes-hopping associated to 3d-ions in high mixed oxidation states. At temperatures above the maximum, in air and oxygen, total conductivity decreases slightly with increasing temperature. This is a common behaviour of oxides associated to oxygen release⁵⁶ increasing concentration of oxygen vacancies results in annihilation of charge carriers (holes) and perturbation of the O–(Fe,Co)–O conduction paths.⁵⁷ Under N_2 total conductivity is much lower and continuously increases with temperature. These facts suggest that the conduction mechanisms operating in this condition may be different compared to oxidising environments. In particular, ionic conduction due to a higher concentration of mobile oxygen-vacancies may play an important role. In any case, in air atmosphere $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ shows much lower electrical conductivities compared to other perovskite-related cobaltites such as $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ ($x = 0.5$ and 0.6)⁵⁸ or $\text{GdBaCo}_{2-x}\text{Fe}_x\text{O}_{6-\delta}$.⁵⁹ It is clear that any structural or electronic effect hindering charge-carriers motion will result in a decrease of conductivity. Thus, from a structural point of view high-symmetry perovskites-like cobaltites should display high electronic conductivity since perovskite structure presents three-dimensional electrical routes through the O–Co–O network facilitating charge-carriers mobility. On its hand, in the R-P structures or layered perovskites the O–Co–O paths are broken in the AO rock-salt layers, in the former (Figure 1), or in the sheets containing the oxygen vacancies in the latter.⁶⁰ According to these ideas, R-P cobaltites with $n > 1$ should present higher electronic conductivity than materials with $n = 1$ due to an increased number of O–Co–O interactions, since the number of perovskite layers increases with n , (Figure 1) However, the structure is not the only material's feature controlling its electronic conductivity. In fact, electronic aspects, such as the oxidation state of Co, play an important role. In this sense, T. Matsuura reported electronic conductivities values at 700 °C of $500 \text{ S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ and $100 \text{ S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ for $\text{La}_{0.5}\text{Sr}_{1.5}\text{CoO}_4$ and LaSrCoO_4 , respectively, both with K_2NiF_4 -like structure (R-P $n = 1$). The conductivity at the same temperature of $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ (R-P $n=2$) is ca. $84 \text{ S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$, slightly lower to that of LaSrCoO_4 .^{61, 62} Thus, it seems that electronic aspects are more important than structural ones. To explain these results, one must focus on the oxidation state of the Co; high electronic conductivity is observed when the oxidation state of the Co is 3.5. The presence of the small Co^{4+} diminishes the average Co–O distance resulting in a better overlap between oxygen-2p and cobalt-3d orbitals enhancing charge transfer (high carries mobility) and consequently increasing electronic conductivity.⁶³

Besides the above-discussed structural and electronic features, other aspects such as the presence of dopants may diminish conductivity. Thus, cubic perovskites $\text{Sr}_2\text{CoNb}_{1-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{O}_{6-\delta}$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1$) show noticeably low conductivity, most likely due to the presence of Ti^{4+} or Nb^{5+} as any pathway involving these cations will be blocked since they can hardly be oxidized accepting a hole, to participate in charge transfer.⁵⁶

Figure 7. Temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity of $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ measured in N_2 , air and O_2 atmospheres.

Polarization tests on symmetrical cells

Figure 8 shows the impedance spectrum of an ESCF1550/CGO/ ESCF1550 symmetrical cell measured in air at 700 °C. In order to separate the different contributions, the impedance spectra were fitted using the Zview software³⁸ to an equivalent circuit shown in the inset of Figure 8. It consists of an inductance, L , caused by the wires of the electrochemical cell and equipment, an ohmic series resistance associated to the overall cell resistance, R_s , and three serial RQ-elements associated to the electrode processes (R =resistance, Q = constant phase element with impedance $Q^{-1}(i\omega)^{-n}$ where the exponent n indicates the similarity to a true capacitor for which $n=1$). This circuitual model can be denoted as $(L)(R_s)(RQ)_{HF}(RQ)_{IF}(RQ)_{LF}$ where HF, IF and LF denote the high, intermediate and low frequency processes, respectively. The final refined parameters for the spectra recorded at different temperatures are given in Table SI 3. The (RQ) values are related to the capacitance (C), and the relaxation frequency (f), which can be calculated according to references^{64, 65} using Equations (2), (3) and (4).

$$C = \frac{(RQ)^{1/n}}{R} \quad (2) \quad f = \frac{\omega}{2\pi} \quad (3) \quad \omega = (RQ)^{-1/n} \quad (4)$$

The high frequency process with capacitance in the range (0.001-1000 μFcm^{-2}) is assigned to charge-transfer processes through the electrolyte-electrode interface.^{39, 66} For the IF process, the capacitance and relaxation frequency are about 10^{-4} Fcm^{-2} and 1-4 kHz, respectively, which are both in the typical range of electron charge transfer processes.^{1, 39, 66, 67} Finally, the low frequencies process (with capacitance from 10^{-2} to 10^{-1} Fcm^2 and

relaxation frequency in the range 1-100 Hz) can be assigned to oxygen diffusion through the electrode pores and exchange at the gas phase/electrode interfaces.^{1, 39, 66, 68}

Figure 8. Impedance spectrum for ESCF1550/CGO/ESCF1550 symmetrical cells at 700 °C in air. The inset shows the equivalent circuit used to fit the spectra. The solid line is the calculated spectrum using the equivalent circuit.

The values of the activation energies for the different processes given in Table SI 3 ($E_a(\text{HF}) = 0.95 \text{ eV}$, $E_a(\text{IF}) = 1.01 \text{ eV}$ and $E_a(\text{LF}) = 1.25 \text{ eV}$) further support the above assignment of processes since they nicely agree with those reported for SOFC materials.⁶⁹ Worth to note, in this paper the identification of the processes is based on the analysis of both the parameters of circuitual models (including E_a) and distribution of relaxation times (DRT) spectra.

The temperature dependence of the ASR values (sum of resistances associated with the different processes obtained by fitting the IS spectra to equivalent circuits), in the range of 550–700 °C, is shown in Figure 9. Similar values are obtained on both heating and cooling cycles, in spite of the slight oxygen loss observed by TGA. As shown in Table SI 3, at low temperature the two similar contributions are responsible for the electrode resistance: i) mass diffusion processes (oxygen diffusion into the pores and exchange through the gas/electrode interface), and ii) electron charge transfer. On the other hand, at higher temperature ASR is mainly due to charge transfer through the electrolyte-electrode interface. In any case, total ASR values are slightly higher than those obtained in similar

materials in the system $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{2-x}\text{Mn}_x\text{O}_7$ ($x = 0.5$)²⁶, however in the present Fe-substituted compound the ASR values are still among the lowest ones reported for R–P oxides. Similar values have been reported for $\text{La}_4\text{Ni}_{2.6}\text{Co}_{0.4}\text{O}_{10+\delta}$ and $\text{NdSrCo}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_x\text{O}_{4+\delta}$ materials, but at significantly higher temperatures.^{21, 23}

Relatively good values of ASR are obtained for symmetrical cells with cathodes of composition $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7/\text{CGO}$ 70:30 (w:w) without optimization of the microstructure of the components of the cell. Thus, as shown in [Figure SI 2](#), although the electrode/electrolyte adhesion is good (without any noticeable defects such as cracking or delamination in the interfaces), the electrodes consist of large particles (micron-sized) of the active materials covered by submicron particles of the electrolyte. This is far from being a proper microstructure to obtain optimal triple-phase boundary conditions.

Figure 9. Arrhenius plot of the area-specific resistance (ASR) values obtained from the impedance spectra of the ESCF1550/CGO/ESCF1550 symmetrical cells on heating in air.

In a very recent paper several n=2 R-P compounds have been studied.²⁸ This paper confirms the decrease of TEC and the increase of ASR as cobalt is replaced by other 3d-metals, already reported in several cases.^{26, 33-35} Interestingly, the best ASR values given in this paper are similar to that we reported for another n=2 R-P material $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Mn}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$,²⁶ to that in the present manuscript. The ASR seems to strongly correlate with Co-content and its oxidation state in the perovskite blocks; thus, a compromise between good catalytic

activity and high electronic conductivity (low ASR) and not too high TEC, both depending on cobalt content, must be reached. On its hand, the exact composition of the rock-salt layers is directly related with ionic conduction (through interstitial oxides or anti-Frenkel defects as in our case), and indirectly with TEC and electron conduction. High TEC of cobalt oxides is due to spin transitions of Co^{3+} ;^{31, 32} stabilization of LS- Co^{3+} can be achieved increasing the crystal field on cobalt ions in CoO_6 octahedral (Oh) environments. The stronger the Co-O interaction the more split are the $t_{2g}(\sigma^*)$ and $e_g(\pi^*)$ orbitals due to the relative stabilization of the $\pi^*(\text{Co-O})$ levels⁷⁰ and the lower the spin state of Co^{3+} limiting spin transitions. For a given anion (oxide in metal oxides) it is possible to modify its electronegativity by the so-called inductive effect with relevant consequences on the materials properties.⁷² In R-P oxides small RE cations, which are more acidic, enhance oxygen electronegativity through inductive effect, which results in a strong crystal field on cobalt ions and a larger splitting between t_{2g} and e_g orbitals. Therefore, the spin state of the cobalt ions in compounds with small RE is lower than in similar oxides with larger lanthanides elements. Stabilisation of LS- Co^{3+} in n=2 R-P oxides will result in lower TEC; thus, the materials with small RE elements may be more adequate for SOFC electrodes. However, as observed in other similar oxides, as the RE-O bonds get stronger, the Co-O bands becomes narrower, so that the p-type conduction will be worse, which could be a serious drawback for the application of these compounds in SOFCs.⁷³ Besides, praseodymium that can present mixed oxidation state has noticeably influence on the redox properties of the material.^{19, 29, 30}

Conclusions

The $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ oxide has been synthesized and studied as potential cathode material for SOFCs. The crystal structure has been determined by X-ray diffraction, high-resolution transmission electron microscopy and STEM. The Eu/Sr distribution over the two crystallographically distinct A-sites has been refined, which reveals complete cationic ordering. Tilting of the Co/FeO₆ polyhedra occurs in the perovskite-like blocks in the structure. More than that, interstitial oxygen atoms are detected within rock-salt like EuO layers. Such features have been determined by HAADF and ABF STEM study.

The thermal stability and chemical compatibility with CGO have been also studied in order to perform electrochemical characterization as prospective cathode materials for IT-SOFCs. Impedance measurements on symmetrical cells using this compound as electrode revealed $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrCo}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_7$ material displays one of the lowest ASR values reported so far for a R-P oxide ($0.26 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ at $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in air), this together with a relatively high conductivity make this material potentially useful for practical application as cathode component in SOFC devices.

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